

Participation of the Azerbaijani Representative at the 11th International Gas Congress (Moscow, 1970)

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Abstract

This working paper, based on the official documents of the 11th International Gas Congress (Moscow, 9–13 June 1970), analyses the nature of participation by Abutalib Mir Aga oglu Abdullaev (in Soviet documents, Abutalib Miragaevich Abdullaev), Head of the Chief Gas Administration under the Council of Ministers of the Azerbaijan SSR (Glavgaz of the Council of Ministers of the Az. SSR), in this international scientific and technical forum. Unlike the [Hamburg Congress of 1967](#), where Abdullaev participated exclusively in an administrative-expert capacity, in Moscow he appeared as a co-author of the official Section D report. The study shows that this change in status reflected both the strategic rise of Azerbaijan within the Soviet gas system following the launch of the IGAT-1 project and Abdullaev's personal professional standing at the all-union level.

Introduction: The Moscow Congress as a Continuation of the Hamburg Trajectory

The 11th International Gas Congress, held on 9–13 June 1970 in Moscow under the auspices of the International Gas Union (IGU), was a logical continuation of the Hamburg forum of 1967. It was at the Hamburg Congress that A. I. Sorokin, the USSR representative, was elected IGU President for the 1967–1970 cycle [1] — and it was under his chairmanship that the organisation moved to Moscow. The Soviet Union served not only as the host country but as the undisputed professional leader of the global gas industry of the period.

The congress took place at a turning point. In 1970, a test launch of the Iranian IGAT-1 pipeline was carried out, with its terminal point at Astara on the Azerbaijani-Iranian border. Although the official inauguration of the pipeline took place in October 1970 [12, p. 40], the preparation of infrastructure on Azerbaijani territory to receive Iranian gas was already well under way by the time the congress convened. This transformed the republic from a regional supplier of gas to Georgia and Armenia into a strategic transit hub providing a key element of the Soviet “gas swap strategy.” That same year, the USSR and the Federal Republic of Germany signed the historic “Gas for Pipes” deal (Erdgasröhrengeschäft) in Essen, opening the era of Soviet gas exports to Western Europe [2]. Azerbaijan's gas transmission system occupied a central place in this architecture: it was through Azerbaijan that Iranian gas entered the Soviet network, freeing up Siberian volumes for European buyers [3].

For Abdullaev, the Moscow Congress was his second international forum of this level. At the 10th Congress in Hamburg (1967), he had attended as a member of the official USSR delegation — without an individual paper, in an administrative-expert role [4, p. 119]. In Moscow, his status changed fundamentally.

Institutional Framework of Participation: From Delegation Member to Presenter

The official congress programme records Abdullaev's participation as co-author of Paper D3 in Section D, "Gas Distribution." The full title of the paper is "Peculiarities of Gasification of Georgia, Armenia and Azerbaijan." Co-authors were G. N. Bardzimov, K. A. Demidov, and R. G. Melikyan (all USSR). In the official list of papers, Abdullaev's name appears first: A. M. Abdullaev [5, report D3].

This circumstance is of fundamental importance. In Soviet academic culture, the order of co-authors typically reflected either scientific contribution or administrative rank. The fact that the head of the republican Glavgaz headed the list of authors of a paper covering three South Caucasian republics testifies to the recognition of Azerbaijan as the leading link in the regional gas system — which directly corresponded to its role in the IGAT-1 project.

The congress participant card and invitation documents from Abdullaev's personal archive confirm his full membership in the official USSR delegation (see Appendices). His participant registration number was 2000, country: USSR. In addition to the sectional sessions, he was invited to the official reception at the State Kremlin Palace hosted by the USSR Ministry of the Gas Industry and the Scientific and Technical Society of the Oil and Gas Industry of the USSR (13 June 1970), as well as to the reception marking the opening of the congress hosted by the State Committee of the Council of Ministers of the USSR for Science and Technology (9 June 1970). Particular attention is deserved by the invitation from A. Clark Dougherty, Chairman (President) of the major American corporation Rockwell Manufacturing Company, to a reception at the Rossiya Hotel (10 June 1970) — evidence that Abdullaev was included in the circle of participants in international business dialogue.

Paper D3 in the Context of Azerbaijan's Gas Strategy

Paper D3 was presented within Section D (IGU Committee on Gas Distribution) — one of the congress's key thematic sections. The section dealt with questions of gasification of settlements, the construction of distribution networks, and the supply of industrial consumers. This subject matter was the most topical for the entire South Caucasus: from the mid-1950s the region had been undergoing accelerated gasification based on Azerbaijan's Karadagh field, and from 1970 on Iranian imported gas.

By the time of the congress, under Abdullaev's leadership, Glavgaz of the Az. SSR had ensured the gasification of all cities and towns in the republic (achieved by 1961) and was preparing infrastructure to receive Iranian gas via IGAT-1.

The co-authorship structure is also telling: G. N. Bardzimov represented the Georgian component, R. G. Melikyan the Armenian. The leading position of the Azerbaijani representative in this collective reflected objective realities: Azerbaijan was the only producer and transit country for natural gas in the region.

Participation in the "Intergas-70" Exhibition

A vivid demonstration of Azerbaijan's growing importance in the USSR gas industry was the large-scale representation of the republic at the International Exhibition of the Gas Industry "Intergas-70," which ran in parallel with the congress in Moscow.

A large delegation of the Chief Gas Administration of the Council of Ministers of the Azerbaijan SSR, headed by Abdullaev, comprising 30 people, participated in the exhibition. It included representatives of all the main subdivisions of the republic's gas economy. Azerbaijani specialists actively familiarised congress participants and foreign guests with the republic's achievements in the gasification, transportation, and use of natural gas. The exhibition stands displayed numerous exhibits and samples of gas equipment manufactured in the Azerbaijan SSR, as well as materials demonstrating the experience of operating trans-Caucasian trunk lines and the preparation of infrastructure to receive Iranian gas [11, p. 98].

Functional Analysis of Participation

Compared with the Hamburg Congress (1967), the functional profile of Abdullaev's participation in Moscow expanded substantially. Whereas in Hamburg his role was confined to three components — expert-managerial support, state representation, and participation in professional discussions — in Moscow a fourth was added: direct authorship of a scientific and technical paper.

Abdullaev's functions at the Moscow Congress included:

- Scientific and technical authorship — presentation of the paper on the peculiarities of gasification of the three South Caucasian republics in Section D of the congress;
- Leadership of the delegation at the “Intergas-70” exhibition — organisation and leadership of the large group of Glavgaz specialists from the Azerbaijan SSR (30 people) presenting the republic's achievements in the gas industry at the parallel international exhibition, which was a striking demonstration of the sharply increased strategic importance of Azerbaijan as a transit hub on the eve of the IGAT-1 pipeline launch;
- Expert-managerial support — evaluation of international technological solutions in the field of gas supply and distribution from the perspective of a leader of a system already receiving Iranian gas;
- State representation — official participation in ceremonial congress events at the level of receptions at the Kremlin Palace of Congresses;
- International business engagement — participation in the Rockwell Manufacturing Company reception and establishment of contacts with foreign partners.

Conclusion

Abdullaev's participation in the 11th International Gas Congress in Moscow marked a qualitative transition in his international professional trajectory. Hamburg (1967) was the point of entry: an experienced republican official found himself for the first time as a member of the Soviet delegation at the world's leading gas forum, without delivering a paper. Moscow (1970) became the point of recognition: the same individual now appeared as co-author of an official paper presenting the South Caucasus as a unified region with a developed gas transmission infrastructure.

This change in status was not accidental. By 1970, Abdullaev had spent more than twenty years building Azerbaijan's gas system — from the Baku Gas Trust “Bakgaz” (from 1942) through the post of Minister of Municipal Economy to Glavgaz under the Council of Ministers of the Az. SSR [6]. A member of the Technical Council of the USSR Ministry of the Gas Industry since 1965 [7]

and a participant in the Hamburg Congress of 1967, he approached the Moscow forum as a specialist whose competence had been recognised at the all-union level.

An important milestone directly in 1970 was the institutional elevation of the organisation he headed: Abdullaev succeeded in securing the withdrawal of the Chief Gas Administration from the structure of the Ministry of Municipal Economy of the Azerbaijan SSR. Glavgaz's acquisition of independent status under the Council of Ministers of the Az. SSR effectively placed the agency on a par with a republican ministry [13, p. 40]. Thus, at the Moscow forum of 1970, he appeared not as an administrator of a regional subdivision of the municipal economy, but as the fully independent and autonomous head of the entire gas industry of a sovereign republic within the USSR.

The Moscow Congress did not mark the end of this trajectory. In 1972, Abdullaev secured the creation of the Baku Main Gas Pipeline Administration (BMGPA) [8], removing the Azerbaijani sections of the trunk lines from under the Transcaucasian Main Gas Pipeline Administration based in Tbilisi. In 1974 he headed the Aztransgaz Production Association [9]. In 1976 he participated, as part of the Soviet delegation, in the IGAT-2 negotiations in Tehran [10]. Hamburg (1967) — Moscow (1970) — Tehran (1976): three forums form a coherent professional arc reflecting both Abdullaev's personal biography and the evolution of Azerbaijan's role in Soviet and international gas policy.

APPENDICES

Documents of the 11th International Gas Congress (Moscow, 9–13 June 1970) from the Personal Archive of Abdullaev

Part I. Registration and Identification of the Participant

Figure 1. Official congress participant badge.

Description: The original lapel badge of A. M. Abdullaev bearing the symbols of the 11th International Gas Congress in Moscow (1970). The badge bears the forum logo ("11g 1970 Moscow"), the country abbreviation "USSR," and the delegate's surname in handwriting. Used as the primary pass for events.

Figure 2. Congress participant card (front side).

Description: The official individual "Participant's Card / Carte de Participant" in blue with the congress emblem and dates: 9–13 June 1970. The inside of the card is completed in the name of Comrade Abdullaev A. M. (USSR), confirming his status as a full member of the Soviet delegation with individual registration number 2000.

Part II. Scientific Programme and Official Paper

Figure 3. Official register of papers of the 11th International Gas Congress (cover and inside page).

Description: Trilingual list of papers of the International Gas Union (IGU). In Section D (“Gas Distribution”) under code D3, the paper “Peculiarities of Gasification of Georgia, Armenia and Azerbaijan” is recorded, with the name of the head of Glavgaz of the Az. SSR, A. M. Abdullaev, listed first among the authors.

D2	А. Г. Туманов, В. П. Максимов, Т. П. Хандога, В. Н. Кальченко (СССР) A. G. Tumanov, V. P. Maximov, T. P. Handoga, V. N. Kaitchenko (USSR)	Natural gas and gas supply of the Ukrainian Soviet Socialist Republic	Gaz naturel et l'approvisionnement en gaz de la République Socialiste Soviétique d'Ukraine	Природный газ и газоснабжение Украинской ССР
D3	А. М. Абдуллаев, Г. Н. Бардзимов, К. А. Демидов, Р. Г. Мелнкян (СССР) A. M. Abdulaev, G. N. Bardsimov, K. A. Demidov, R. G. Melikjan (USSR)	Peculiarities of gasification of Georgia, Armenia and Azerbaijan	Les particularités de la gazéification de la Géorgie, l'Arménie et l'Azerbaïdjan	Особенности газификации Грузии, Армении и Азербайджана
D4	А. В. Железняков, Ч. С. Крукаускас, Л. Я. Писарчик, В. А. Генералов (СССР) A. V. Gelesnjakov, Ch. S. Krukauskas, L. Ya. Pisarchik, V. A. Generalov (USSR)	Gasification and gas supply of Lithuania, Latvia and Estonia	La gazéification et l'approvisionnement en gaz de Lituanie, Lettonie et Estonie	Газификация и газоснабжение Литвы, Латвии и Эстонии
D5	П. Б. Заровный (СССР) P. B. Zarowni (USSR)	Municipal gas for RSFSR towns	Gaz pour les besoins domestiques des villes en RSFSR	Газ для коммунально-бытовых нужд РСФСР
D6	У. Д. Мамаджанов, В. А. Ермишев, А. Е. Соломонов, А. С. Мельситдинов (СССР) U. D. Mamadjanov, V. A. Ermishev, A. E. Solomonov, A. S. Melsitdinov (USSR)	Gas and gas supply in Central Asia	Gaz et gazéification de l'Asie Centrale	Газ и газоснабжение Средней Азии
D7	А. Л. Уревич (СССР) A. L. Ourevitch (USSR)	Gasification and gas supply system of Byelorussian Soviet Socialist Republic	Gazéification et distribution du gaz en République Socialiste Soviétique de la Biélorussie	Газификация и газоснабжение Белорусской ССР
D8	Н. В. Ж. Кемпен (Нидерланды) X. В. Дж. Кемпен (Голландия)	Influence of natural gas on plants and trees	L'influence du gaz naturel sur la verdure	Влияние природного газа на зеленые насаждения

Part III. Protocol and Business Events of the Congress (in chronological order)

Figure 4. Invitation to the state opening of the congress (9 June 1970).

Description: Official government invitation card addressed to Comrade Abdullaev A. M. from the State Committee of the Council of Ministers of the USSR for Science and Technology. Event: ceremonial reception marking the opening of the congress in the Banquet Hall of the Kremlin Palace of Congresses, Tuesday, 9 June 1970, 20:30.

Figure 5. Invitation to the international business reception of Rockwell (10 June 1970).

Description: Bilingual invitation card addressed personally to Comrade Abdullaev A. M. from A. Clark Dougherty, Chairman (President) of the major American corporation Rockwell Manufacturing Company. The reception was held on Wednesday, 10 June 1970 at 18:30 in the restaurant on the ground floor of the Rossiya Hotel (Kremlin side), confirming Abdullaev's integration into the top tier of international business dialogue.

Figure 6. Invitation to the final government banquet (13 June 1970).

Description: Protocol invitation addressed to Comrade Abdullaev A. M. from the USSR Ministry of the Gas Industry and the Scientific and Technical Society of the Oil and Gas Industry of the USSR. Event: official closing reception in honour of congress participants in the Banquet Hall of the Kremlin Palace of Congresses, Saturday, 13 June 1970, 20:30.

Part IV. Parallel Exhibition Activity

Figure 7. Invitation to the International Exhibition “Intergas-70.”

Description: Official Invitation Card to the International Exhibition of the Gas Industry “Intergas-70,” held at the Exhibition of Achievements of the National Economy of the USSR (VDNKh) in parallel with the congress. It was here that A. M. Abdullaev led the large delegation of Glavgaz of the Azerbaijan SSR, consisting of 30 specialists, demonstrating the republic’s achievements and the readiness of its infrastructure for transit via the IGAT-1 project.

References

1. International Gas Union. Transactions / Compte rendu / Schlußbericht. Vol. 1: General Section. 10th International Gas Conference. Hamburg: IGU; 1967.
2. Nies S. Oil and Gas Delivery to Europe: An Overview of Existing and Planned Infrastructures. Brussels/Paris: IFRI-ARIS; 2008.
3. Central Intelligence Agency. Economic Implications of Soviet-Iranian Agreements Involving Oil and Gas. Intelligence Memorandum RR IM 67-29. Washington, D.C.: CIA; 1967 (Declassified 1998). https://www.cia.gov/readingroom/docs/DOC_0000381440.pdf

4. International Gas Union. List of Participants / Liste des Congressistes / Teilnehmerliste. 10th International Gas Conference. Hamburg: IGU; 1967 June 6–10.
5. International Gas Union. List of Papers Presented for the 11th International Gas Conference in Moscow. Moscow: IGU; 1970 June 9–13.
6. Archive of Political Documents of the Presidential Administration of the Republic of Azerbaijan. Personal file of Abdullaev Fund (f.) 1, inventory (in.) 87, No. 33.
7. Appointment Letter of Abdullaev to the Technical Council of the USSR Gas Industry State Production Committee (1965). Zenodo; 2026. <https://zenodo.org/records/20341812>
8. ID Card of Abdullaev — Head of the Baku Main Gas Pipeline Administration (BMGP), 1972. Zenodo; 2026. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19711604>
9. ID Card of Abdullaev — Director of the Aztransgaz Production Association (Aztransgaz), 1974. Zenodo; 2026. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20185900>
10. Aztransgaz Production Association. Soviet-Iranian Negotiations on IGAT-2 in 1976: Photograph from a Working Dinner at the Copacabana Restaurant (Tehran) Featuring Abdullayev. Zenodo; 2026. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20366547>
11. State Archive of the Azerbaijan Republic (SAAR). Orders of Glavgas Nos. 223–440 on General Issues, 1970. Fund 3084, inventory 1, No. 33., f. 3084, in. 1, No. 33.
12. SAAR. Correspondence with the Council of Ministers of the Azerbaijan SSR on Measures to Improve the Safety of Urban Gas Supply for 1970. F. 3084, in. 1, No. 37.
13. Archive of Azerigas Production Association. Personal File of A.M.A. Abdullaev. F. 2, in. 1, No. 277.